

Characterization and Gas sensing properties of Graphene nanoribbons/ Indium trioxide / Polyaniline Nanocomposites

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ABSTRACT

In this study, graphene nanoribbons (GNR) were prepared by longitudinal unzipping of multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs). Graphene nanoribbons (GNR)-indium trioxide (In_2O_3) hybrid materials were prepared by a solvothermal reaction of an indium precursor containing GNR. Finally, the graphene nanoribbons/indium trioxide/polyaniline (GNR/ In_2O_3 /PANI) composite was prepared by in-situ polymerization method for ammonia detection. In ammonia gas sensing, the addition of mesoporous In_2O_3 nanoparticles and GNR can significantly improve the sensing performance as compared to that of pure PANI. This result indicated that the GNR/ In_2O_3 /PANI sensor showed highest response value of 21.9 at 4 ppm NH_3 at room temperature, which was about 2.7 times higher than that of pure PANI. The enhancement of sensing performance for the GNR/ In_2O_3 /PANI nanocomposite was attributed to synergistic effect of p-n junction of PANI and mesoporous In_2O_3 nanoparticles with high surface ratio.

Experiment

Fig 1: The preparation process of GNR / In_2O_3 / PANI hybrid nanocomposites.

Fig 2: Schematic illustration of home-made gas sensing test system.

Characterization results

Fig 3: The XRD pattern of GNR, In_2O_3 , GNR/ In_2O_3 , PANI and GNR/ In_2O_3 /PANI.

Fig 4: The FTIR spectrum of GNR, In_2O_3 , GNR/ In_2O_3 , PANI and GNR/ In_2O_3 /PANI.

Fig 5: The TEM images of (a) In_2O_3 nanoparticle, (b) GNR/ In_2O_3 hybrid and, (c) GNR/ In_2O_3 /PANI nanocomposite.

Ammonia-sensing properties

Fig 6: (a) Dynamic response-recovery curves of pure PANI and GNR/ In_2O_3 /PANI, (b) The repeatability of GNR/ In_2O_3 /PANI. (4ppm NH_3 at room temperature)

Fig 7: The (a) dynamic response curves, and (b) response-concentration fitting curves of GNR/ In_2O_3 /PANI thin film sensors toward 2.1-5.7 ppm NH_3 at room temperature.